

Results and Discussion

The relative changes of viscosity i.e., $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$ during slow coagulation of ferric tellurate sol in the presence of $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$ have been plotted against time (Fig. 1) at different temperatures. Similar figures were obtained with other sols. For ferric tellurate and chromium tellurate sols the experiments were carried out at 20°, 30°, 40°, and 50°. For chromium tellurate sol the electrolyte used was $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$. The coagulation of vanadium pentaoxide sol was studied in the presence of $5.6 \times 10^{-4} M BaCl_2$ at 25°, 35°, 45° and 55°.

Fig. 1. Coagulation of Ferric Tellurate Sol at different temperatures with $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$.

The logarithm of time of slow coagulation ($\log t_s$) has been plotted against $1/T$ for each of the sols studied (Fig. 2). All the plots have yielded straight lines

Fig. 2. $\log t_s$ Vs $1/T$.

confirming the validity of the equation (1).

The value of NV_{max} for ferric tellurate sol in the presence of $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$ is calculated from the slope of the plot. This is equal to 9356 cal., the value of $N E$ for water being 3305 cal./mole¹². Similarly for chromium tellurate sol in the presence of $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$ the value of $N V_{max}$ has been found to be 10285 cal., and for vanadium pentaoxide sol in the presence of $5.6 \times 10^{-4} M BaCl_2$ this has been found to be 8495 cal.

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Condensation of Deoxybenzoin with Aldehydes

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THE present investigation deals with the condensation of deoxybenzoin with a number of aldehydes in Knoevenagel's reaction. The identity of the products were established on the basis of analysis and IR absorption spectrum (Table 1).

NOTES

TABLE I—ABSORPTION PEAKS (CM⁻¹) OF CHARACTERISTIC GROUPS OBTAINED IN THE I.R. SPECTRA (KBr DISC) OF THE VARIOUS CONDENSED PRODUCTS

S.No.	X	X'	C=O	Aromatic C=C		C—H bending for trisubstituted alkene	Aromatic C—NO ₂	Phenolic C—O stretch- ing ³⁽¹⁾
1 ^a	—OCH ₃	H	1709	1626, 1600, 1460		801	—	—
2 ^b	—OCH ₃	H	1681	1616, 1665, 1527, 1429		820	—	—
3	H	OH	1690	1600, 1500, 1450		799	—	1225
4 ^c	Cl	H	1712	1629, 1590, 1473, 1441		806	—	—
5 ^d	Cl	H	1681	1592, 1495, 1429		810	—	—
6	—NO ₂	H	1678	1613, 1600, 1527, 1460		800	1313	—
7	H	—NO ₂	1681	1613, 1600, 1504, 1460		800	1313	—

a = compound of melting point 95°.

b = compound of melting point 178°.

c = compound of melting point 116°.

d = compound of melting point 220°.

Experimental

Preparation of Deoxybenzoin: It was prepared by the method adopted by Donald A. Ballard and William M. Dehn¹.

5-Bromo and 3 : 5-dibromo salicylaldehyde—These were prepared as reported earlier².

Condensation with Anisaldehyde: Equimolecular amounts of deoxybenzoin and anisaldehyde were heated under reflux at different temperatures viz., 120, 140 and 160° for different durations of time viz. 6, 12 and 18 hours in the presence of different bases viz Pyridine, Piperidine, α -picoline, a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride and a mixture of triethylamine and acetic anhydride. The condensed product so obtained was boiled in petroleum ether and filtered. The filtrate on concentration gave a product (A) m. p. 95°. (Found, C, 83.61; H, 5.43; C₂₂H₁₈O₂* requires C, 84.07; H, 5.7%). The residue on recrystallisation with alcohol gave another product (B) m.p. 178°. (Found, C, 83.56; H, 5.23; C₂₂H₁₈O₂* requires C, 84.07, H, 5.7%). As the two compounds A and B gave the same analysis and showed the peaks for the same groups in the I. R. spectrum, they appear to be geometrical isomers of 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*p*-methoxy-phenyl) ethylene**. Maximum yield 47.2% of the condensed product was

obtained when the reactants were heated for 12 hours at 160° in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride as the catalyst.

Condensation with salicylaldehyde: The condensed product on crystallisation with alcohol acetone mixture was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-1-(*o*-hydroxy phenyl) ethylene, m. p. 99°. (Found, C, 83.73; H, 4.82; C₂₁H₁₆O₂ requires C, 84; H, 5.33%). Maximum yield 95.3% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 140° in the presence of piperidine as the catalyst.

Condensation with *p*-Chlorobenzaldehyde: The condensed product was boiled in ligroin and filtered. Filtrate on crystallisation yielded a compound (A) m.p. 110°. (Found, C, 78.5; H, 4.5, C₂₁H₁₅ClO₂* requires C, 79.1; H, 4.7%). The residue on recrystallisation with ethanol gave another product (B) m.p. 220°. (Found, C, 78.9; H, 4.2; C₂₁H₁₅ClO₂* requires C, 79.1; H, 4.7%). As the two compounds A and B gave the same analysis and showed peaks for the same groups in the I.R. spectrum, they appear to be geometrical isomers of 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*p*-chlorophenyl) ethylene. (See table I). Maximum yield 89.7% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 12 hours at 140° in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride as the catalyst.

* 1-Benzoyl-1-Phenyl-2(*p*-methoxyphenyl) ethylene

** See Table I

* 1-Benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*p*-Chlorophenyl) ethylene.

Condensation with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde : The condensed product on recrystallisation with petroleum spirit was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*p*-nitrophenyl) ethylene, m.p. 89° (Found, N, 3.8; C₂₁H₁₅NO₃ requires N, 4.2%). Maximum yield 60% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 12 hours at 160° in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride as the condensing agent.

Condensation with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde : The condensed product on crystallisation from petroleum spirit was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(*o*-nitrophenyl) ethylene, m.p. 150°. (Found, N, 3.6; C₂₁H₁₅NO₃ requires N, 4.2%). Maximum yield 60% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 160° in the presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride as the catalyst.

Condensation with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde : The condensed product on crystallisation from alcohol acetone mixture was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-bromo-phenyl) ethylene, m.p. 115°. (Found, Br, 20.9; C₂₁H₁₅BrO₂ requires Br, 21.1%). Maximum yield 98.5% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 160° in the presence of piperidine as the catalyst.

Condensation with 3 : 5-dibromosalicylaldehyde— The condensed product on crystallisation from alcohol acetone mixture was found to be 1-benzoyl-1-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3' : 5'-dibromo-phenyl) ethylene, m.p. 105°. (Found, Br, 34.6; C₂₁H₁₄Br₂O₂ requires Br 34.9%). Maximum yield 85.6% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hours at 120° in the presence of piperidine as the condensing agent.

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Studies on Solvation of Ions in Nonaqueous Media : Part-I. Whether the Apparent Molal Volumes of Strong Electrolytes in DMSO is an Additive Property ?

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IN our previous studies¹, apparent molal volumes of some 1 : 1 electrolyte e.g. NaBr, NaI, NaNO₃, KBr, KNO₃, CsI and R₄NI (R = CH₃⁺ to C₇H₁₅⁺) have been reported at different concentrations and the values of limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ° , have been obtained by the extrapolation of almost straight lines ϕ_v vs $|\bar{C}$ curves to zero concentration. The results were discussed in the light of solute-solvent interaction. Due to limited data in DMSO, it was not possible and justified at that time to test the additivity of limiting apparent molal volume in this solvent. It may be mentioned here that the ϕ° values of electrolytes are found to be additive in solvents of high dielectric constant and strong hydrogen bonding like water², formamide³ and N-methyl propionamide (NMP)^{4,5}. Dimethylsulphoxide differs much from these solvents, having no hydrogen bonding and the dielectric constant ($\epsilon_{25^{\circ}} = 46.6$) is also much lower than the above group of solvents. Therefore, it seems quite desirable to test the additivity of ϕ° of electrolytes in DMSO before evaluating limiting ionic molal volumes to have a more clear picture of ion-solvent interaction in DMSO. Keeping this in view, apparent molal volumes of few more 1 : 1 electrolytes, namely, KI, CsBr, NH₄Br, NH₄I, NH₄NO₃ in DMSO have been determined at different concentrations and temperatures. The ϕ° values have been obtained from the ϕ_v vs $|\bar{C}$ curves and the additivity is tested.

Experimental

The salts used were all of B.D.H., A. R. grade, except NH₄I which was of U.S.S.R. pure grade. These salts were further purified by repeated crystallisation from conductivity water before use. The purified crystals were dried to a constant weight in a hot air oven and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The rest of the experimental procedure for determining density and calculating the apparent molal volumes therefrom was the same as detailed earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

From the ϕ_v data, ϕ_v vs $|\bar{C}$ curves were drawn for various salts at different temperatures. These curves were almost linear with a positive slope for all the salts studied here, similar to those for the other common salts reported earlier¹. By the extrapolation of these straight lines to zero concentration, limiting apparent molal volumes, ϕ° , are obtained for various salts at

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